

**ANALYSIS OF CULTURAL CODE CHARACTERISTICS OF
LANGUAGE UNITS RELATED TO SUPERSTITIONS IN UZBEK
LINGUISTIC CULTURE**

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Annotation: In this article, the characteristics of the cultural code in language units related to rituals existing in the Uzbek linguistic culture are analyzed using the examples of the number component. On the basis of the obtained conclusions, the characteristics of the cultural code in the language units related to rituals in Japanese and Uzbek linguistic culture are subjected to a linguistic and cultural comparative analysis.

Key words: superstitions, ethnographic language, cultural code, social life

Superstitions are considered one of the main sources of the ethnographic language layer, in which certain views of the people are concentrated. The trinkets were a means of transferring various experiences from everyday life from generation to generation. Of course, not all strata of the people work based on customs, but there are certain customs that have become a daily activity or habit in the life of the people. Superstitions entered people's life on various grounds, in particular, on the basis of various conclusions made on the basis of observation of events; on the basis of the preservation of moral rules or imaginary views that depend on the original religious views; based on views embedded in the content of events in ancient narratives; That's why the scope of the subject of the stories is wide. Because it is an ethnographic process of special importance in the context of social life. In the language of every nation in the world, the subject range of mysteries formed on the basis of explanation of certain events, textual solutions to

mysterious concepts, or stagnation of mystical views is very wide. In particular, it is possible to study the scope of the topics of the idioms, which appear in the Uzbek language as an ethnographic unit, divided into several groups by means of images.

Superstitions appeared as an imaginary solution to various life foundations that have been passed from the beginning of the processes of formation of this nation to the present day.

The factors of the emergence of idioms in the ethnographic layer of the Uzbek language are considered different and can be divided into the following types: 1- idioms with vital foundations. Although there is no connection between the thought and the secret in such rituals, a certain action is disappointment or unpleasantness may occur. For example, the saying “don't leave the broom standing upright, it will be bad” is not related to the fact that certain disappointment will occur based on the essence, but it may become unfit for work due to damage to three parts caused by leaving it upright. is intended, and by associating it with a certain sense of the divine, a mystery has arisen based on an attempt to dissuade the addressee from this work.

2. Secrets that are completely far from the fundamentals of life. There is no connection between the thoughts and the words spoken in such rituals.

We will analyze the linguistic and cultural features of cultural code formation in language units related to number rituals through examples.

Linguistic units related to rituals with a numerical component in the Uzbek language culture were collected from the book “Reformation of Heresies and Superstitions” by Odilkhan Qori Yunuskhan’s son and also from the book “Annotated Dictionary of Uzbek Language Entographisms” by N. Mirzayev. In the Uzbek linguistic culture, language units related to rituals with a number component are divided into two groups according to their form:

The first is its appearance as a component of a complete syntactic unit:

1. It is impossible to wash a newborn baby and remove his hair and nails.

In example 1, the word “forty” is involved in the language unit related to secret. Here, forty components express two different meaningful relationships. The first is the number forty, which refers to the expectation that forty days will pass before the birth of a baby, because in the life of Uzbeks there is a chilla season that lasts forty days. The word “chilla” is explained in the “Explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language” as follows: chilla - [forty days]

1.The forty hottest or coldest days of the year. Chilla entered. Chilla came out. Although it was still early, the sun was shining brightly. “Sharq yulduzi”.

Summer chill or summer chill is the hottest forty days from June 25 to August 5. August is summer chill. “The sharp sun of my city is really burning”

H. Nazir, Maftuningman, Azerbaijan.

“Chilla water” - water given to crops in summer chilla. Winter chilla or winter chilla is the coldest forty days from December 25 to February 5. “The cold of winter came very hard.” S. Ahmed, "Silence."

2. ethnicity. The period of forty days after the birth of a child, the marriage of a girl, the marriage of a young man, the day of the burial of the deceased: the most difficult, dangerous or responsible period of some events in marriage. "When the baby was born, they moved to a new house, Yoshlik. In folk medicine, the period of chilla is considered to be forty days, of which twenty days are small chilla and twenty days are called big chilla “UzME”. Cold sore, a rash that appears in a child during cold weather. “Shohrat got a cold sore on his head and neck and it lasted for six months.”- Q. Kenja, “One evening on the mountain road”.

The chilla has not come out - 1) the chilla period has not ended. “Next week, you will be discharged from the hospital. We were going to have a party, even if I didn't want to go out”. Sh. Kholmiraev, “If a heavy stone moves”. “I told you forty times, dear bride, there are bad mouths in the village, they will laugh, at least put on this jacket and go to work until you get cold. “Yoshlik” 2) portable:

inexperienced; cave, raw. 3 - religion. A sufi or murid prays alone in a separate room (hujra), hiding from people, for forty days. To sit quietly - 1) in the Sufi order: to pray in solitude without leaving the house for forty days.

In example 2, the seasonal meaning of the word “forty” is used, and the meaning of the baby’s most responsible, life-environment learning period is activated. The number “forty” has become a whole compound together with a special idiomatic unit in the form of "forty to come out”.

2. It is a sin for the owners of the old household to eat eggs until the deceased is “forty”.The ethnographic character of the word “forty” has been activated in the structure of this secret, as in example 2. Therefore, the number “forty” is “the most important” in Uzbek linguistic culture the first forty days are coded as ". The reason for this is the existing traditions of the ethnographic way of life of the people.

3. Tapping the money of the first item sold on top of the items they are selling
The ordinal number “first”was involved in the ethnographic language unit related to this ritual. In this case, the first content of the “first” number is activated. The number “forty” in these rituals is coded as “responsible period” in Uzbek linguistic culture. The first number is culturally coded as “the beginning of the trade”.

In the examples 1-2-3 analyzed above, the expressions with the number component were accompanied by a certain syntactic content. There are also special rituals with numbers in the Uzbek linguistic culture. In the Uzbek linguistic culture, the numbers three, four, seven, nine, forty, as well as even numbers and odd numbers express a special meaningful relationship.

Resources

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